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Review Article

**SONOGRAPHIC CORRELATION BETWEEN ENDOMETRIAL
POLYPS WITH INFERTILITY: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW****Maoz Ahmad^{1,3}, Dr Sayyeda Khadija¹, Namrah Shahid¹, Rahman Ud Din^{2,3},
Sadia khanum khattak³, Laiba Gul³**¹ Department of Radiology, University of Lahore Pakistan² Department of Biomedical Engineering, Faculty of Environment and Life Science, Beijing
University of Technology, Beijing, China.³ Department of Medical Imaging and Radiology, Northwest Institute of Health Sciences
affiliated with Khyber Medical University Peshawar Pakistan.**Article Received:** October 2020 **Accepted:** November 2020 **Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

Introduction: Endometrial polyps (EPs) found in approximately 34.9% of infertile women. Transvaginal sonography (TVS) is a regularly, non-invasive module of fertility evaluation. Most ultrasonographic studies of EPs have occurred on abnormal uterine bleeding; few have assessed EPs in infertile women. Moreover, no studies have explored endometrial thickness and its association with EPs in infertile women. This study aimed to evaluate transvaginal sonographic measurement of endometrial thickness and its value in analysis and prediction of EPs in infertile women.

Purpose: This systematic review is conducted to find the role of ultrasound in detection of endometrial changes which causes polyps infertility in women.

Method: The English literature (MEDLINE, PUBMED, and OBGYN.ONLINE LIBRARY) was searched using keywords endometrial polyps; transvaginal sonography; endometrial thickness; infertility; All abstracts were prospective studies between 2010-2020. Relevant articles were assessed.

Conclusion: TVS is poor in detecting of EPs in infertile women; on the other hand, transvaginal sonographic measurement of endometrial thickness is useful. It is recommended that the diagnostic importance of TVS for EPs in infertile women can be better by adding the measurement of endometrial thickness to the variables that are regularly assessed.

Keywords: Infertility, Endometrial Thickness, Endometrial polyps, Transvaginal scan.

Corresponding author:**Maoz Ahmad,**

Department of Radiology, University of Lahore Pakistan

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INTRODUCTION:

Endometrial polyps (EPs), a common endometrial disease, occur in approximately 25 per cent of women and up to 34.9 per cent of infertile women.^{1,2} EPs are typically benign, pedunculated surface growths originating from the basal endometrial layer. Whereas large EPs appear to present as abnormal uterine bleeding, small EPs in frequently menstruating women are typically associated with abnormal uterine bleeding with infertility. The relationship between EPs and fecundity remains uncertain, as does the mechanism by which EPs lead to infertility. These mechanisms which include mechanical interaction with sperm transport, implantation of blastocysts or aberrant expression of implantation markers.³ some studies⁴⁻⁷ indicated that infertile women should undergo hysteroscopic polypectomy. Removal of polyps can boost both the spontaneous pregnancy rate and the pregnancy rate after intrauterine insemination. Some authors propose that combined endoscopic procedures (laparoscopy and hysteroscopy) allow for a timely and full recognition of all factors that lead to a woman's infertility and help ensure higher rates of pregnancy over shorter periods. Intervals, but the view is contentious. Transvaginal Sonography (TVS) is used for the evaluation of endometrial thickness and abnormality in endometrial and myometrial morphology. A normal, non-invasive portion of fertility assessment, TVS may be used to diagnose EPs. Subsequent removal of any polyps by selective hysteroscopy can improve fertility. However, most ultrasound studies have concentrated on EPs in patients with abnormal uterine bleeding;⁸⁻¹¹ few findings concern intrauterine lesions associated with infertility.^{2, 12} Published research primarily concentrate on contrasting TVS with other approaches or predictive value of TVS in intrauterine disorders in general; TVS has the potential to diagnose EPs in infertile women. In addition, no researcher has examined endometrial thickness and its relationship with EPs in infertile women. The present study was designed to test TVS measurement of endometrial thickness and its use in the diagnosis and prediction of EPs in infertile women.

METHODS:**Search strategy:**

We searched PUBMED, COCHRANE, MEDLINE, OBGYN.ONLINE LIBRARY. For words in title abstract an MeSH terms. All words like endometrial polyps; transvaginal sonography; endometrial thickness and infertility were used.

Study selection:

We reviewed multiple articles, and then excluded Prospective, case control and case reports from data, we applied additional methodological filter for paper selection and selected papers published between (2010-2020).

Only Retrospective studies reporting on prevalence, risk, symptoms, using Transvaginal sonography were included.

RESULTS:

Using the search criteria 10 researches were examined based on the title and abstract. All the 10 studies were considered in their full versions. Of these works, including literature review reports, it was concluded that ultrasound grayscale and Doppler studies has a positive correlation between endometrial polyps and infertility.

SYSTEMATIC REVIEW:

Total of 10 original articles were reviewed which addressed Endometrial polyps relations with Infertility.

1. In a retrospective study conducted by Maryam Niknejadi, (M.D.et al in 2010) included Of 679 patients who underwent hysteroscopy, endometrial polyps were diagnosed in 197 (24.5%) patients. TVS confirmed the presence of endometrial polyps in 174 out of 197 cases (88.3%), however misdiagnosed 23 cases of polyps as normal endometrium. In 482 women, no polyps were detected during hysteroscopy. TVS was agreement with 443 (91.9%) of hysteroscopy and in 39 cases sonographic finding was suggestive of polyp. Hysteroscopy was considered as gold standard. Of the 482 hysteroscopy cases who were negative for polyps, additional findings included: normal endometrium (257/482), short septum (82/482), long uterine septum (35/482), leiomyomas (24/482), intrauterine adhesions (17/482), endometrial hyperplasia (15/482), unicornuate uterus (9/482), and didelphys (2/482).
2. In retrospective study conducted by Sabri Cavkaytar .et al in 2014 Between January 2012 and January 2014, 328 operative hysterectomies were performed in postmenopausal women for resection of endometrial polyps. Premalignant and malignant polyps were identified in 26 (7.9%) of cases. Sonographic measurement showed a greater endometrial thickness in cases of premalignant and malignant polyps when compared to benign polyps. On surgical hysteroscopy, premalignant and malignant polyps were also larger. Endometrial thickness demonstrated a sensitivity of 53.8%, specificity of 85.8%, PPV of 24.6% and NPV of 95.6% at a

- cut-off limit of 11.5 mm with diagnostic accuracy of 83.2%. Polyp size has a diagnostic accuracy of 94.8% with a sensitivity of 92.3%, specificity of 95.0%, PPV of 61.5% and NPV of 99.3% at a cut-off point of 19.5mm.
3. In retrospective study conducted by Devleta Balic et al in 2011 included, in this retrospective study 56 infertile patients were included with abnormal ultrasound appearance of the uterine cavity. The mean age of the subjects was 31.9/4.0. The most frequent ultrasound finding was endometrial polyp in 34 (60.7%) patients, septate uterus in 8 (14.3%) patients, submucosal myoma in 7 (12.5%) patients, and endometrial hyperplasia in 5 (8.9%) patients and Syndrome Ascherman in 2 (3.6%) patients. Hysteroscopy confirmed 20 (35.7%) polyps, the same number of myomas, septate uterus and Syndrome Ascherman as detected by ultrasound, (7 (12.5%), 8 (14.3%) and 2 (3.6%), respectively) and 19 (33.9%) endometrial hyperplasia. In 46 women with histological examination, the sensitivity of TVS and hysteroscopy in the diagnosis of endometrial polyps were identical - 100%, while the specificity was higher in hysteroscopy than in TVS (92.3% versus 56.4%, $p < 0.001$). The sensitivity of TVS in the diagnosis of endometrial hyperplasia was higher than that of hysteroscopy (86.4% versus 22.7%, $p < 0.001$), while specificity was identical, of 100%. Accordance between hysteroscopy and histology was good ($k=0.79$), between ultrasound and histology was moderate ($k=0.59$).
 4. In retrospective study conducted by SONG Yong et al in 2012 included Based on recognized criteria, TVS had a sensitivity of 37.04%, specificity of 98.71%, positive predictive value of 90.91%, negative predictive value of 81.85%, and accuracy of 82.80% for diagnosing EPs. Mean endometrial thickness was significantly different in patients with and without EPs ($P=0.0001$). In women in the mid and late-proliferative phase, the endometrial thickness was significantly greater in those with EPs than in those without them ($P=0.0001$ and 0.024). Receiver operating characteristic analysis showed that endometrial thickness had a sensitivity of 85.2% and specificity of 38% in the diagnosis of EPs, the area under the curve being 0.64. In the mid-proliferative phase, sensitivity was up to 90.9%, the area under the curve being 0.70.
 5. In retrospective study conducted by Judit Lőrincz et al 2019 included, mean age of patients was 33.99 ± 4.24 years. There were no differences in the BMI and basal FSH levels between the subgroups. Pregnancy was recorded in 30 (34.5%) within the next 12 months without any difference between the subgroups of polypectomy method applied. Posterior wall polyp resection increased the pregnancy chance (OR 5.02), but no other differences were observed in 1-year pregnancy rates to other localizations. Removal of polyps which had normal endometrial histology had lower pregnancy rates as compared to that of polyps with hyperplasia or endometrial polyp histology results (OR 0.25).
 6. In retrospective study conducted by Catherine H. Phillip et al included A total of 1274 patients received a baseline TVS as part of a work up for infertility during the study period. We identified infertility patients prior to initiation of assisted reproductive technology who had baseline TVS, HSG, and HSC within 180 days of each other. From medical record review, we compared frequencies of each finding between modalities. Of the 1274 patients who received a baseline TVS over 2 years, 327 had TVS and HSG within 180 days and 55 patients had TVS, HSG and HSC. Of the 327, TVS detected fibroids more often than HSG (74 vs. 5, $p < .0001$), and adenomyosis more often than HSG (7 vs. 2, $p = .02$). HSG detected tubal obstruction more often than TVS (56 vs. 8, $p = .002$). Four (1.2 %) patients had endometrial polyps on both HSG and TVS. In the 55 patients with HSG, TVS, and HSC, HSC identified endometrial polyps more often than TVS (10 vs. 1, $p = .0001$) and HSG (10 vs. 2, $p = .0007$). TVS detected more fibroids than HSC (17 vs. 5, $p < .0001$). Tubal obstruction was identified more often by HSG than HSC (19 vs. 5, $p < .0001$).
 7. In retrospective study conducted by Licong Shen conducted in 2011 included , Of the 431 infertile patients, 158 (mean age 31.0 ± 4.2 y, mean body mass index [BMI] 20.6 ± 2.5 kg/m²) had laparoscopy-proved endometriosis (stage I, 77; stage II, 27; stage III, 36; stage IV, 18), and 273 (mean age 30.7 ± 5.3 y, mean BMI, 20.8 ± 2.6 kg/m²) had no endometriotic foci found during laparoscopy. The mean age, BMI, and duration of infertility did not differ between the endometriosis and nonendometriosis groups . Endometrial polyps were found in 108/158 women cases (68.35%) with endometriosis and in 56/273 of the control participants (20.51%), which was significantly different ($P < .01$). The frequencies of endometrial polyps for each stage of endometriosis were 63.64% (49/77) in stage I, 70.37% (19/27) in stage II, 72.22% (26/36) in stage III, and 77.78% (14/18) in stage IV

(P¼.18). The prevalence of endometrial polyps in ovarian endometriosis was higher (46/60, 76.67%) than that in pelvic or peritoneal endometriosis (62/98, 63.27%), but the difference was not statistically significant (P¼.08). Because 11 patients were lost to follow-up by telephone questionnaires or mail, the clinical pregnancy rate was analyzed in the remaining 420 women (152 in the endometriosis group and 268 in the non-endometriosis group). There were 167 clinical pregnancies, and the pregnancy rate was 39.76% (167/420). Of these 167 pregnancies, 103 patients had live births, 7 patients underwent spontaneous abortions, and the remaining 57 patients had not yet delivered (3 in first trimester of pregnancy, 54 after first trimester).

In the endometriosis group, the pregnancy rates were 49.52% (52/105) for patients after hysteroscopic polypectomy and 29.79% (14/47) for those without polyps (P<.05). Furthermore, of the 105 patients after hysteroscopic polypectomy, the patients in the early stages (stages I and II) of endometriosis achieved significantly higher clinical pregnancy than those in the advanced stages (stages III and IV; 63.64% [42/66] vs. 25.64% [10/39], respectively; P<.01) and those without polyps in the early stages (stages I and II) of endometriosis (37.14% [13/35]; P<.05). However, in the nonendometriosis group, the clinical pregnancy rate was not significantly different between infertile women after hysteroscopic polypectomy and those without polyps (42.86% [24/56] vs. 36.32% [77/212], respectively; P¼.37).

8. In retrospective study concluded by Filomena Marino Carvalho et al 2013 included, Signs of endometritis, vascular changes and polyps were identified in 176 (40.5%), 168 (38.6%) and 102 (23.4%) cases, respectively. There was a significant association between endometritis and vascular changes. The more frequent vascular alteration (70%) was the hyaline thickening of vessels, a morphological pattern very similar to the thick-walled vessels of polyps. Polyps were associated with endometritis in 28 (27.4%) cases and with other vascular changes besides the vascular stalk in 14 (13.7%). All the polyps with vascular changes had histologic evidence of endometritis. There was a significant association between inflammatory phenomena and vascular changes, even among cases of polyps.
9. In retrospective study conducted by Atsushi Yanaihara et al 2007 included, The incidence of endometrial polyps was as follows, by location: uterotubal junction, 8.0%; posterior uterine wall,

32.0%; anterior uterine wall, 15.4%; lateral uterine wall, 9.2%; and multiple, 35.4%. The pregnancy rate after surgery was as follows, by location: uterotubal junction, 57.4%; posterior uterine wall, 28.5%; anterior uterine wall, 14.8%; lateral uterine wall, 18.8%; and multiple, 40.3%. Endometrial hyperplasia was found in 6.9% of the cases. The pregnancy rate after surgery at the uterotubal junction was significantly higher than that of other locations.

10. In retrospective study conducted by S. Salim, H.Won et al 2011 included, Clinical outcomes after treatment of endometrial polyps are generally good. In a randomized clinical trial of 150 women with an endometrial polyp allocated to hysteroscopic removal or observation, there was no difference identified in the volume of menstrual loss between the groups, although the symptoms, such as intermenstrual bleeding, were significantly improved by removal at follow-up (residual symptoms following polyp removal 7/75 vs conservative 28/75; p 5.001)¹³. Other studies report the symptomatic improvement to be very good, with abnormal uterine bleeding resolved after hysteroscopic polypectomy in 75% to 100% of cases.^{14, 15} Adhesion risk is low after polypectomy, because the myometrium is not incised and the endometrium has an excellent regenerative capacity¹⁶.

A class I study with 90 women reports no adhesions after hysteroscopic polypectomy, and routine antiadhesion treatments are unlikely to be of benefit in this group of patients¹⁷. In a class II-3 retrospective study, recurrence of polyps after 9 years of follow-up after hysteroscopic polypectomy was reported in 5 of 240 patients (3.7%), requiring repeat hysteroscopic removal in 3 (1.7%) and subsequent hysterectomy in 2 (0.8%)¹⁸. This is in contrast to a class II-3 study that reports recurrence of symptoms after polypectomy of 60% by survival curve analysis; however, only 2/78 (2.5%) women were identified to have recurrent polyps, with many other diseases present in the remaining patients including abnormal uterine bleeding¹⁹.

This indicates that although recurrence of polyps is low, the presenting symptoms leading to surgical removal are not always related to the presence of the polyp. It is therefore important to differentiate recurrence of disease with recurrence of symptoms, and discussion of this fact with the patient before intervention is required. Most of the data for polypectomy in subfertile patients suggests that removal improves fertility, with reported pregnancy rates varying between 43% to 80%^{18, 20, 21}. Both

spontaneous pregnancy rates and those associated with assisted reproductive technology are reported to be increased after polypectomy. In a class I study, polypectomy before intrauterine insemination significantly increased subsequent pregnancy success (relative risk 2.1, 95% CI 1.5-2.9, $p < .001$). The rate of pregnancy in the study group was 51%, and of these, 65% had a spontaneous conception before the first intrauterine insemination, whereas all Pregnancies in the control group were obtained during the fertility treatment²². There is conflict surrounding the size of polyp needed to be removed to achieve an improvement in assisted reproductive technology, with data suggesting that removal of polyps, 2 cm has no impact on the outcome of fertility treatment.^{23,24} In contrast, a class II-2 study suggested that restoration of fertility was not dependent on the size of lesion removed (139) and a class II-3 study reported no significant difference in the reproductive outcome for patients with polyps ≥ 2.5 cm or < 2.5 cm.¹⁸

CONCLUSION:

A total of 10 articles were reviewed for endometrial polyps related to the infertility. Hysteroscopy and TVS used for investigating the endometrial polyps possess relation with infertility. TVS is a regularly, non-invasive module of fertility evaluation except it is poor in detecting of EPs in infertile women but TVS measurement of endometrial thickness is useful. Most ultrasonographic studies of EPs have occurred on abnormal uterine bleeding; few have assessed EPs in infertile women. Moreover, no studies have explored endometrial thickness and its association with EPs in infertile women. It is recommended that the diagnostic importance of TVS for EPs in infertile women can be better by adding the measurement of endometrial thickness to the variables that are regularly assessed.

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